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Examination of Internal Validity and Reliability of an Elicited Imitation Task (EIT): A FACETS Approach

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Abstract

Elicited imitation tasks (EITs) are considered a useful and quick way to establish a second language users' oral proficiency. In this study, we examine the internal validity of the EIT task used by Wu and Ortega (2013). Internal validity refers to the extent to which a causal relationship can be demonstrated to exist between independent and dependent variables. In this case, the independent variable is the EIT items' lengths in syllables, while the dependent variable is EIT scores. EIT data were collected from Japanese university students ($N = 102$) and analyzed using the many-faceted Rasch model approach. The findings provide evidence for EIT internal validity and reliability. Suggestions for creating EITs are offered.

Key words: elicited imitation task (EIT), oral proficiency, validation, Rasch

1. Background

1.1 What Are Elicited Imitation Tasks (EITs)?

The elicited imitation task (EIT), sometimes referred to as a sentence repetition task (SRT), requires test subjects to listen to a sentence and then repeat it as accurately as possible. Accurate repetition, it is argued, requires linguistic processing beyond mere memorization (Slobin & Welsh, 1973). EITs are thus considered a quick method of establishing general L2 (second language) proficiency. These tasks emerged in the late 1960s when researchers like Slobin and Welsh (1973) explored their use in developmental psycholinguistics.

EITs have been adopted and refined for various languages and contexts. Ortega et al. (1999) developed and validated EITs for English, German, Japanese, and Spanish. Additional studies have reported results of EITs conducted in Mandarin (Wu & Ortega, 2013; Zhou & Wu, 2009) and Vietnamese (Chaudron et al., 2005). Interest in EITs, particularly among second language acquisition (SLA) researchers, has grown over time and spread worldwide.

1.2 Possible Pedagogical Applications of EITs

EITs have significant potential applications in language classrooms and assessment of linguistic proficiency. Applications range from initial linguistic proficiency measurement for streaming purposes, to informing classroom pedagogy, and finally to tracking development over time. Using EITs for initial assessment of target language proficiency offers some considerable benefits over traditional proficiency measures like written exams and oral interviews (Kato & Tanaka, 2015). Those measures can be time-consuming and might not accurately reflect students' productive language ability. EITs potentially provide an expedient and objective alternative approach.

Because working memory capacity is limited, longer utterances cannot be easily stored in working memory. Graham et al. (2010) argued that the L2 learners must draw upon their L2 knowledge and employ information chunking to accurately reproduce the aural input. For this reason, EITs can be indicative of not only overall target language fluency but also specific aspects of linguistic proficiency such as grammar, syntax, vocabulary, and pronunciation.

EITs have also been found to correlate well with other language proficiency measures, such as interviews and standardized tests (Suzuki & DeKeyser, 2015; Tracy-Ventura et al., 2014). Although EITs are useful for evaluating structural language use, they might not fully capture deeper aspects of lexicogrammatical knowledge, such as spontaneous lexical choice or more complex grammatical constructions (Kim et al., 2016; Vinther, 2002). Furthermore, because short EIT responses can sometimes be memorized, they might not always reflect learners' ability to produce language freely in real-world contexts.

There are also potential applications of EIT results for independent study and classroom interventions. EIT feedback can direct language learners and teachers

to focus on areas of language proficiency that require the greatest attention. EIT feedback encompasses an assessment of students' language proficiency, including their lexicogrammatical knowledge. This feedback often evaluates learners' morphosyntactic accuracy and lexical choices, providing insights into their understanding of vocabulary and grammatical structures. Research shows that EITs are effective for measuring fluency, syntactic complexity, and overall language use, which are critical for developing second language skills (Kim et al., 2016; Tracy-Ventura et al., 2014). When EIT feedback is immediate or rapid, evidence suggests students more readily recognize their mistakes. This fosters a more interactive and responsive learning environment (Erlam, 2006). Similarly, EIT results can be interpreted at the individual or group level by language teachers and curriculum designers to appropriately tailor instruction and materials to students. This personalized approach can lead to greater student engagement and more effective learning (Gaillard & Tremblay, 2016).

Finally, EITs can be used to monitor students' progress over time to track target language proficiency improvements and continually adjust instructional strategies as appropriate. Furthermore, Jessop et al. (2007) have also found evidence suggesting EITs induce less student test anxiety. EITs are generally perceived as less intimidating than formal exams because they involve natural language use. This establishes a relaxed and supportive testing environment, encouraging students to perform their best without undue pressure.

1.3 Previous Studies Establishing Evidence of EIT/SRT Reliability

Several studies provide evidence regarding the statistical reliability of EITs across languages, with Cronbach's alpha (α) ranging from .93 to .99. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the strength of the internal consistency of scale items with possible values ranging from 0 to 1. Typically, a Cronbach's alpha of .70–.80 or greater is considered sufficiently reliable (Field, 2018). Examples of prior EIT studies that measured EIT reliability include the following: Chaudron et al. (2005), $\alpha = .99$ (Vietnamese, $N = 28$); Cox and Davies (2012), $\alpha = .94$ (English, $N = 179$); Gaillard and Tremblay (2016), $\alpha = .93$ to $.97$ (English, German, Japanese, Spanish, $N = 150$); Graham et al. (2006), $\alpha = .94$ (English, $N = 81$); Spada et al. (2015), $\alpha = .95$ (English, $N = 72$); and Wu and Ortega (2013), $\alpha = .97$ (Chinese, $N = 80$).

Findings extend beyond EIT reliability as well. For instance, Wu and Ortega's (2013) study involved forty L2 learners of Mandarin Chinese and forty heritage speakers. The EIT scores significantly differentiated between low-level and high-level learners, with an effect size (Cohen's *d*) of 2.84, suggesting strong discriminative power. Tracy-Ventura et al. (2014) found moderate to strong correlations between French EIT scores and measures of lexical complexity ($r = .62$), speech rate ($r = .67$), and university end-of-year grades ($r = .78$), thereby supporting the test's concurrent validity. Furthermore, Suzuki and DeKeyser (2015) examined the validity of EITs and word monitoring tasks among L1 (first language) Chinese speakers learning Japanese, finding that EIT performance was related to spontaneous corrections of ungrammatical uses of particles and correlated with working memory capacity. Additional studies from Erlam (2006) and Jessop et al. (2007) further established EITs as valid measures of implicit linguistic knowledge, emphasizing their potential to distinguish between levels of language proficiency and their low susceptibility to rote memorization. Collectively, these findings suggest EITs reliably measure linguistic proficiency and are predictive of other linguistic proficiency metrics, making them valuable for proficiency assessment and research.

1.4 Current Gap in the Literature

There is a notable gap in the research literature regarding the application of EITs in the Japanese context. This study seeks to demonstrate the utility and reliability of a 30-item version of the EIT (Ortega et al., 1999; Tracy-Ventura et al., 2014). An EIT adapted for a Japanese context could serve as a reliable and practical tool for assessing linguistic proficiency, offering advantages for both educational settings and SLA research in Japan. Such an instrument would enable more accurate measurement of language skills and facilitate cross-linguistic comparisons, thereby enriching our understanding of language acquisition processes across different linguistic and cultural contexts (Suzuki & DeKeyser, 2015).

1.5 Research Questions

In order to address the current gaps in the literature for a 30-item EIT and its application in the context of Japanese learners of English, the following research

questions were developed:

RQ1. To what extent does the EIT demonstrate internal validity and reliability as a measure of English speaking proficiency for Japanese learners of English?

RQ2. How reliable is the 0–4 rating scale for raters of EITs in assessing L2 learners' oral proficiency?

RQ3. What is the relationship between sentence syllable count and task difficulty for Japanese learners of English?

Many-facet Rasch measurement (MFRM) was used to assess the reliability of the EIT and the functionality of the 0–4 rating scale. Internal validity was investigated by using a Pearson correlation to compare the participants' MFRM scores with the number of syllables on the EIT items. These findings were then compared with previous EIT research findings.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

Data were collected from Japanese students at a top-ranked national research university located in western Japan. The participants were recruited based on their participation in one of a variety of study tours abroad to countries, such as Australia, Taiwan, and Vietnam. The participants ($N = 102$; 70% female) were predominantly first-year students ($n = 76$), with a smaller representation from second-year ($n = 15$) and third-year ($n = 11$) students. The participants were enrolled in the following academic disciplines: architecture, economics, law, engineering, literature, various sciences, and education. The education majors included sub-specialties such as elementary education, English education, and social studies, among others.

The participants' overall TOEIC scores were $M = 618$ ($SD = 114.5$, range = 380–870). The participants' TOEIC listening scores were $M = 319$ ($SD = 62.7$), and their reading scores were $M = 299$ ($SD = 65.1$).

2.2 Instrument: Elicited Imitation Task

The EIT (Ortega, 2002) consists of students listening to and imitating 30 English sentences of varying lengths and complexity. These items were first created by Ortega et al. (1999). See Appendix A for the 30 sentences. The sentences vary in length from seven to 19 syllables. Sample sentences for the EIT include *I have to get a haircut* (shortest sentence) and *There are a lot of people who don't eat anything at all in the morning* (longest sentence). We used the same five-point, holistic rating scale used by Ortega et al. (2002) (see Appendix A).

We recorded the 30 EIT sentences as separate audio files. We cleaned the audio to ensure optimal fidelity, volume, and to eliminate background noise. Three seconds of silence followed by a quick, clear beep was then added to the end of each audio file. The three seconds began immediately after the final syllable of the target sentence had been uttered. The beep cued participants to begin their attempt at repeating the sentence.

2.3 Data Collection Procedure

EIT samples were collected via one-on-one sessions in a quiet office space. Sessions began with an initial greeting, a chance for the participant to ask questions, and a 5- to 10-minute conversation in English. The EIT exercise was then explained, and participants then practiced on a sample item. Participants wore studio quality headphones and were informed the volume was adjustable if necessary. EIT items were collected in order from 1 to 30. Participants were provided as much time as necessary to attempt repeating the sentence. Upon completing their attempt, the subsequent item was played.

Each EIT sample was rated by at three L1 English speakers, all of whom were American graduate students living in Japan. Raters completed their ratings over the course of one day in the same office space. The ratings process began with a 10-minute explanation of the rating scale and was followed by the raters individually rating the EIT responses from a single participant. After rating all 30 utterances produced by the participant, the raters shared their ratings with each other. Any differences in ratings were discussed by the raters to ensure they used the rating scale appropriately.

Each rater rated two-thirds of the participant data sample. Rating assignments were staggered as follows. Rater 1 rated the first two-thirds of the sample. Rater 2

rated the second two-thirds of the sample. Rater 3 rated the first one-third and the last one-third of the sample. This ensured all samples were rated by two raters, and that there was equal rater overlap. This is essential for calculating Rasch reliability and potential differences in rater severity. After completing all ratings, raters compared their ratings to ensure their ratings were not wildly different. They were encouraged to discuss differences in rating but were free to leave their ratings as they were or adjust them post-discussion.

2.4 Data Analysis: Many-Facet Rasch Measurement

A many-facet Rasch model (MFRM), developed by Linacre (1994), along with the FACETS software package (Linacre, 2011) was used to analyze the participants' EIT scores, rater behavior, and to investigate the construct validity of EIT test items. MFRM is beneficial when multiple raters are used to assess performances because it provides information about rater severity, within-rater consistency, rater bias, and rater agreement that can be analyzed. It also provides equitable scores that account for rater-dependent differences (Koizumi et al., 2017, p. 244). Put another way, the raters' scores are adjusted based on how severe or lenient their ratings tend to be. In this way, the scores of the participants are not impacted due to being assessed by a harsher or easier rater. This is especially important for studies such as this one where the participants were not assessed by all three raters.

In addition to providing rater data, Rasch fit statistics can be used to identify erratically-performing participants and poorly performing test items. Fit is indicated by how accurately the person performances conform to the Rasch model's predictions based on person ability and item difficulty measurements. Fit is measured as infit mean square (MNSQ) and outfit MNSQ. MNSQ is a chi-square statistic that is divided by its degrees of freedom and has an expected value of 1.00. Linacre (n.d.-a) recommends first analyzing MNSQ outfit then MNSQ infit. If misfit is identified, infit standardized z scores (ZSTD) and outfit ZSTD should also be investigated.

Infit MNSQ is sensitive to unexpected patterns where person ability measures are near item difficulty measures whereas, outfit MNSQ is sensitive to unexpected differences when person ability and item difficulty measures are far apart. Infit is more sensitive to the overall pattern of responses, while outfit can be influenced by just a few

outliers (Linacre, n.d.-a). MNSQ infit and outfit statistics of 1.00 represent a perfect fit to the Rasch model. A fit statistic that is higher than 1.00 for infit MNSQ indicates that the participant who is near the item's difficulty did not answer the item as predicted while higher than 1.00 outfit scores indicate that a high ability person made a mistake on a relatively easy item, or a low ability person got a relatively difficult item correct.

While underfit can indicate a problem with a participant or an item, overfit as indicated by infit or outfit MNSQ statistics that are less than 1.00 reveal that the scores are too invariant, overinflating reliability estimates. Underfit is generally thought to be more problematic than overfit because it results in poorer measurement of the latent variable. According to Linacre (2002), mean-square values less than 0.50 indicate a degree of overfit that is less productive for measurement. Infit and outfit MNSQ values of 0.50–1.50 are considered productive for measurement, and while MNSQ values of 1.50–2.00 do not degrade measurement, they are considered unproductive. Values greater than 2.00 degrade the measurement of the construct and require a closer inspection of problematic items or persons, which could serve as evidence justifying their removal from the study.

The Rasch model also provides separation indices as indicators of reliability. Person separation is “an estimate of the spread or separation of persons on the measured variable. It is expressed in standard error units, that is, the adjusted person standard deviation divided by the average measurement error” (Bond et al., 2021, p. 337). Person separation is affected by sample size, sample ability variance, test length, the number of categories for each item, and sample-item targeting (Linacre, n.d.-b). Item separation is “an estimate of the spread or separation of items along the measured variable. It is expressed in standard error units, that is, the adjusted item standard deviation divided by the average measurement error” (Bond et al., 2021, p. 334). Item separation is affected by person sample size and item difficulty variance (Linacre, n.d.-b). A wide range of person abilities results in increased person separation. Similarly, item separation increases when the test items cover a broad spectrum from very easy to very difficult for the test takers.

When the model fit is good, a test that has good separation of person measures and item difficulty measures should be replicable if the population samples are similar. Linacre (n.d.-b) expressed the formula for Rasch person reliability as $(OV-EV)/OV$,

where OV represents the observed variance of person ability measures and EV is the mean of the squared standard errors of person ability measures. Item reliability uses this same formula except OV represents item observed variance and EV represents the mean squared standard errors of item difficulty measures. In this study, we used Fisher’s (2007) criteria for person and item reliability where less than .67 is poor, .67 to .80 is fair, .81 to .90 is good, .91 to .94 is very good, and greater than .94 is excellent.

3. Results

3.1 Items

The Rasch item reliability estimate was excellent at 1.00, and the separation statistic was 15.24 logits. This separation statistic indicates that there was a substantial spread of item difficulty from easy to difficult. Of the total 30 items, 27 had MNSQ infit and outfit statistics between 0.50–1.50. Each item received scores ranging from 0–4, resulting in five possible scores for each item. The Rasch probability curves in Figure 1 indicate that the five possible scores for each item (0–4) are functioning well because each score represents a distinct probability of occurrence across the latent trait,

Figure 1. *Probability Curves for Rater Item Assessments*

Note. Each number 0–4 represents a possible score from a rater where higher scores indicate higher EIT task proficiency. The scores are measured in logits from -4.0 to 4.0, where 0.0 represents the mean participant scores.

and there is no significant overlap between categories. Rasch probability curves are graphical representations used to show how well items are functioning across different levels of the latent trait being measured.

Furthermore, understanding the impact of syllable count on task difficulty can aid educators in refining their instructional strategies. Recognizing that passages with more syllables pose greater challenges, educators can design practice materials and teaching activities that gradually increase in complexity. This can help learners build L2 verbal proficiency in managing longer sentences.

Regarding item misfit, Item 6 misfit with an infit MNSQ statistic of 1.63 and outfit MNSQ of 1.60. This is above 1.50, which means that this item is providing more noise than meaning but not to the extent that it distorts the analysis. Items 1 and 2 had severe misfit to the Rasch model. Item 1 misfit with an infit MNSQ statistic of 1.96 and outfit MNSQ of 2.03, while Item 2 had an infit MNSQ statistic of 2.51 and outfit MNSQ statistic of 2.44, meaning that these items distorted the analysis. We suspect Item 6 misfitting can be attributed primarily to the fact that it is the first interrogative included in the EIT (e.g., *What did you say you were doing today?*).

As a result of these three items that misfit above 1.50 MNSQ infit and 1.50 MNSQ outfit, the analysis was run again with Items 1, 2, and 6 removed from the model to investigate whether there was significant justification for the removal of these items. The model with these items removed resulted in minimal difference from the original. The removal of these items resulted in the variance explained by Rasch measures to decrease from 61.52% to 61.20%. Item reliability was 1.00 for both models, but item separation increased from 15.24 to 15.49 with the new model. The new model had a .01 increase in person reliability from .95 to .96. Similarly, person separation also improved from 4.46 to 4.63. However, based on recommendations by Linacre (2010), it was decided that the fit criteria for item removal was too severe, so the decision was made to retain all items and continue with the original model. However, these misfitting items were investigated and will be addressed in Section 5.

3.2 Persons

The Rasch person reliability estimate was excellent at .95, and the separation statistic was 4.46 logits. This separation statistic means that there was a considerable

disparity in the participants' proficiency on the EIT. Person MNSQ statistics of 0.50–1.50 are productive of measurement, and of the total 102 participants, no one had infit or outfit MNSQ fit statistics less than 0.40 or greater than 2.00. Three participants had infit and/or outfit MNSQ between 0.40 and 0.50, suggesting overfit, meaning their data were overly predictable. Ten participants had infit/outfit MNSQ greater than 1.50, suggesting that these participants' statistics were noisy, but not to the extent that it degraded measurement.

The analysis was rerun with these misfitting participants removed to identify if their removal significantly improved the model. The model with these participants removed resulted in minimal difference from the original. In the new model, the variance explained by Rasch measures increased from 61.52% to 62.26%, but the Rasch person reliability estimate remained the same at .95. Person separation increased from 4.46 to 4.53. Item reliability remained the same at 1.00, but item separation decreased from 15.24 to 14.46. Because no participants had MNSQ fit statistics greater than 2.00 and the removal of these participants only had a minimal effect on the variance explained by the Rasch measures, no participants' data were removed from the study.

3.3 Raters

Raters had a Rasch reliability estimate of .98 and a separation statistic of 9.07. The Rasch reliability statistic for raters is high due to 9.07 logits of spread in rater severity and low measurement error Linacre (n.d.-b). It is important to note that Rasch reliability refers to the ability to distinguish raters based on their severity, not interrater reliability, which focuses on agreement between raters.

Intrarater reliability, or the consistency of each rater's severity estimates across persons and items, can be assessed through MNSQ fit statistics Linacre (n.d.-a). Ideally, MNSQ values close to 1.00 indicate a good fit to the Rasch model. The raters' infit MNSQ values ranged from 0.96 to 1.03, and outfit MNSQ values ranged from 1.00 to 1.03, indicating that, despite a 9.07-logit spread in their rating severity, the raters were highly consistent in applying their rating severity across different items and persons. See Table 1 for the Rasch descriptive statistics for raters.

Because the raters convened after the initial ratings were given and allowed to discuss and adjust ratings for participants in the case that their ratings were substantially

different, it is possible that the differences in rater severity between raters was somewhat minimized. However, because the raters’ rating severity varied by 9.07 logits, and this was measured after the adjustments had been made, we can safely assume that the raters were substantially different in their rating severity.

Unlike other methods of statistical measurement, differences in rater severity are not a problem for Rasch measurement because it accounts for differences in rater severity and uses these data to create fair ratings for the participants. Allowing the raters to reassess ratings that are substantially different was not done for the purpose of improving interrater reliability, but as a means of identifying potential rating mistakes and resolving them.

Table 1. *Rasch Descriptive Statistics for Raters*

Rater	Total score	M	Fair-M	Meas.	SE	Infit MNSQ	Outfit MNSQ
1	3552	1.70	1.77	0.42	0.03	1.03	1.05
3	4012	1.90	1.95	0.13	0.03	0.96	1.00
2	4157	2.00	2.09	-0.07	0.03	1.00	1.01

Note. Fair-M = Fair measure; Meas. = Rasch measure; MNSQ = mean-square.

3.4 Sources of Difficulty

A Pearson correlation analysis was used to investigate the potential relationship between syllable count and item difficulty using data from the Rasch measures. Prior to the analyses, the assumptions required for conducting the analysis were checked and met. The result of the analysis showed a Pearson’s correlation of $r(28) = 0.73, p < .001$. Based on criteria from Field (2018), correlations greater than .50 are considered strong. By squaring $r(28) = 0.73$, we find that syllable count explains approximately 53.29% of the variance in item difficulty. This finding is in line with Graham et al.’s (2010) EIT study that found that sentence length as measured in syllables accounted for 73% of the variance in the EIT scores for their sample of 81 participants (p. 67). The Wright map below (see Figure 2) provides visual information in logits for participants, raters, and items. Participants who are higher on the scale performed better than those who are

lower on the scale. Raters who are higher on the scale were more severe than those lower than them. Items that are higher on the scale were more difficult for the participants than lower items.

4. Discussion

The results of the study suggest that the EIT was an internally valid and reliable measure of the Japanese participants' spoken English foreign language proficiency. The internal validity of the EIT is supported by the clear relationship between the EIT items' lengths in syllables (independent variable) and participants' EIT scores (dependent variable). Syllable count significantly and strongly correlated with the participants' EIT scores, with $r^2 = 0.53$, indicating that sentences with more syllables tended to be more difficult for the participants. Like Wu and Ortega's (2013) study, which found that the EIT was able to discriminate between high and low EIT participant scores, with an effect size (Cohen's d) of 2.84, we found that the participants' scores had a spread of 4.46 logits, supporting the discriminate power of EITs. Our findings align with Graham et al.'s (2010) and Wu and Ortega's (2013) EIT studies that found sentence syllable counts to explain $r^2 = 0.73$ and $r^2 = 0.74$ of the variances in EIT scores, respectively.

Figure 2. *Rasch EIT Wright Map*

Note. The figure has been abridged to fit on one page. $N = 102$. * = 2 participants; . = 1 participant; measure = scores measured in logits. The items are coded 1–30 based on their order in the EIT.

Although the current study did not investigate additional measures of spoken L2 proficiency, Tracy-Ventura et al. (2014) have found EIT scores to correlate with university end-of-year marks, oral interview performances, and speech rate on oral narratives.

Additionally, the data fit the Rasch model well, showing high reliability, with 1.00 for items and .95 for persons, indicating consistency in measuring proficiency across participants and items. These high reliability scores suggest that the EIT is likely generalizable to similar populations. The high Rasch intrarater reliability of .98 and 9.07 logits of differences in rater severity indicates that raters, were significantly different in their severity in ratings. However, their MNSQ infit ranging from 0.96 to 1.03, and outfit ranging from 1.00 to 1.03 suggest that they were self-consistent in how they applied their ratings through the 0–4 rating scale (Koizumi et al., 2017), and would likely provide similar ratings to similar participants on similar items. The distinct probability curves in Figure 1 further illustrate that each rating from 0 to 4 was clearly delineated, with little overlap among the raters according to the scale. Finally, the item reliability of 1.00 further supports the EIT's ability to consistently distinguish between proficiency levels of the participants.

The observed correlation suggests that sentence length, as measured by the number of syllables, plays a critical role in determining EIT difficulty. This finding has practical implications for designing verbal language assessments. Test developers should consider sentence length in syllables when creating test items to better align with learners' proficiency levels and ensure that assessments accurately reflect their language abilities.

5. Limitations and Recommendations for Future Studies

This study aimed to assess the internal validity and reliability of the EIT for measuring English L2 proficiency among Japanese EFL (English as a foreign language) learners. While we found the EIT to have internal validity and to be a reliable measure of spoken English proficiency, our study has limitations in terms of concurrent validity. Specifically, the study did not include comparisons with other established verbal proficiency tests. As a result, the concurrent validity of the EIT remains uncertain.

Previous research, such as Wu and Ortega (2013), demonstrated that EIT scores significantly correlated with narrative performance, while Tracy-Ventura et al. (2014) found significant correlations between EIT performance and university end-of-year grades, oral interview scores, and picture narrative speech rate. The absence of such comparisons in this study limits our ability to evaluate how well the EIT aligns with other measures of verbal proficiency.

Furthermore, other factors that can contribute to EIT difficulty such as lexical frequency, lexical density, syntactic complexity, morphological complexity, L2 phonological differences, differences in aural input rate, etc., were not investigated. Future research should incorporate a broader range of established tests to establish the concurrent validity of the EIT more comprehensively and consider a wider range of factors that contribute to EIT difficulty.

Finally, Items 1, 2, and 6 demonstrated poor fit to the Rasch model in our study. We suspect this might be due to the participants' insufficient acclimation to the EIT task. In the case of Item 6, misfit might have occurred because it was the first case of an interrogative sentence. Once task familiarity improved, item fit was within the acceptable ranges. Therefore, we recommend that future EIT studies and assessments include practice EIT items to facilitate task familiarization. These practice items should be separate from the actual EIT assessment.

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Appendix A

1. I have to get a haircut. (7)
2. The red book is on the table. (8)
3. The streets in this city are wide. (8)
4. He takes a shower every morning. (9)
5. It is possible that it will rain tomorrow. (12)
6. What did you say you were doing today? (10)
7. I doubt that he knows how to drive that well. (10)
8. After dinner I had a long, peaceful nap. (11)
9. I enjoy movies that have a happy ending. (12)
10. The houses are very nice but too expensive. (12)
11. The little boy whose kitten died yesterday is sad. (13)
12. That restaurant is supposed to have very good food. (13)
13. You really enjoy listening to country music, don't you? (14)
14. She just finished painting the inside of her apartment. (14)
15. Cross the street at the light and then just continue straight ahead. (15)
16. I wish the price of townhouses would become affordable. (15)
17. The person I'm dating has a wonderful sense of humor. (15)
18. I want a nice, big house in which my animals can live. (14)
19. I hope it will get warmer sooner this year than it did last year. (16)
20. A good friend of mine always takes care of my neighbor's three children. (16)
21. Before he can go outside, he has to finish cleaning his room. (16)
22. The most fun I've ever had was when we went to the opera. (16)
23. The terrible thief whom the police caught was very tall and thin. (17)
24. The number of people who smoke cigars is increasing every year. (17/18)
25. The exam wasn't nearly as difficult as you told me it would be. (18)
26. She only orders meat dishes and never eats vegetables. (15/16)
27. The black cat that you fed yesterday was the one chased by the dog. (16)
28. Would you be so kind as to hand me the book that is on the table? (17)
29. I don't know if the 11:30 train has left the station yet. (18)
30. There are a lot of people who don't eat anything at all in the morning. (19)

Rating Scale

0 = Silence, only one word repeated, or unintelligible repetition

1 = Repetition of half of the stimulus or less

2 = Changes in content or in form that affect meaning

3 = Accurate content repetition with some (ungrammatical or grammatical) changes of form

4 = Perfect repetition (imperfect pronunciation that does not interrupt rater understanding is acceptable)